

Echo based water level management system using 8051 microprocessor

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Abstract

Classical water management systems i.e water level indicators based on the principle of electrical conductivity of water, gives inaccurate or unreliable reading. To solve these issues this paper proposes the non contact water management system using ultrasonic technology and microprocessor 8051. This water level controller can monitor and control water tanks up to 2m deep and the accuracy of measuring is as low as 0.1cm. Since no mechanical float switches or electrodes are used here, there will not be any mechanical wearing or corrosion and this makes the system highly reliable. Any way proper care must be given to insulate the ultrasonic ranging module from damping as it contains a lot of electronics.

1.Introduction

Data acquisition methods are becoming of major importance in today's industries. The collection of data from liquid tanks plays an essential role in many industrial applications, such as oil tanks, fuel containers, public water supplies, reverse osmosis (RO) systems and fish aquariums. A range of methods was proposed to collect data from liquid tanks using different types of sensors, based on doppler effect[1-2], pressure & liquid pressure variation with depth [3-4], level indicator based on electrical conductivity of water [5]. However, each technology has its strengths and weaknesses under different conditions, leading to a number of challenges for the research community to consider, including feasibility, accuracy, installation cost, reliability.

The aim of this work is to propose an efficient, low cost and precise device for simultaneously monitoring the level and volume of liquids inside the tanks based on detection of the reflected echoes from liquid surfaces using an ultrasonic sensor [6] and Microprocessor 8051. The proposed system has good reliability, high resolution, low cost, is easy to implement, easy to program, portable and has low power consumption.

Ultrasonic sensors seem promising in this regard for liquid data monitoring, since they have high accuracy, low cost and can work with pressures of up to 2 megapascal (MPa), temperatures of up to 100 °C, and ranges up to 30 m [2,7].

2. Design and Methodology

In this paper the microprocessor is interfaced with HC-SR04 [8] ultrasonic module without any contact with water. The circuit diagram of the experimental measurement system is shown in Figure

2.1 HC-SR04 ultrasonic ranging module.[8]

HC-SR04 is the ultrasonic ranging module used here. HC-SR04 consists of an ultrasonic transmitter, receiver and necessary electronics for making it a stand alone system. The operating principle is very simple. It sends 8 pulses of 40KHz sound waves, and picks up the reflected wave. The time lag between the transmission and reception is measured and the distance is calculated from the equation $D=TS/2$. Where D is the distance, T is the time lag and S is the speed of sound.

The output of the HC-SR04 will be a pulse whose width is proportional to the distance. From the datasheet, the width of the output signal will be 58uS for a distance of 1cm. What we need to do is to just send a 10uS wide trigger signal to the trigger pin of the module and wait for the output pulse at the echo pin of the module. Timing diagram and pin out of the ultrasonic module is given below.

Fig.1

- 1) **VCC** : 5V DC supply voltage is connected to this pin.
- 2) **Trigger**: The trigger signal for starting the transmission is given to this pin. The trigger signal must be a pulse with 10µs high time. When the module receives a valid trigger signal it issues 8 pulses of 40KHz ultrasonic sound from the transmitter. The echo of this sound is picked by the receiver.
- 3) **Echo**: At this pin, the module outputs a waveform with high time proportional to the distance.
- 4) **GND**: Ground is connected to this pin.

From the timing diagram, you can see that the 40KHz pulse train is transmitted just after the 10µs triggering pulse and the echo output is obtained after some more time. The next triggering pulse can be given only after the echo is faded away and this time period is called cycle period. The cycle period for HC-SR04 must not be below 50mS. The distance can be calculated from the echo pulse width using the following equations[9].

$$\text{Distance in cm} = \text{echo pulse width in } \mu\text{S}/58$$

$$\text{Distance in inch} = \text{echo pulse width in } \mu\text{S}/148$$

2.2 Microprocessor 8051

The 8051[10] microcontroller was designed by Intel in 1981. It is an 8-bit microcontroller. It is built with 40 pins DIP (dual inline package), 4kb of ROM storage and 128 bytes of RAM storage, 2 16-bit timers. It consists of four parallel 8-bit ports, which are programmable as well as addressable as per the requirement. An on-chip crystal oscillator is integrated in the microcontroller having crystal frequency of 12 MHz.

In the following diagram, the system bus connects all the support devices to the CPU. The system bus consists of an 8-bit data bus, a 16-bit address bus and bus control signals. All other devices like program memory, ports, data memory, serial interface, interrupt control, timers, and the CPU are all interfaced together through the system bus.

Fig.2 Microprocessor 8051

2.3 Circuit Design

Trigger pin of the ultrasonic module is connected to P3.0 of the microcontroller. The Echo pin of the module is connected to P3.1 of the microcontroller. Data lines of the LCD module are interfaced through Port0 of the microcontroller. The control lines RS, RW and E of the LCD module are connected to

P2.7, P2.6 and P2.5 pins of the microcontroller respectively. The pump is controlled using Port 2.0 of the microcontroller. The pump used here is a 12V automobile windscreen washer pump. Mains operated pumps will also go with this circuit but their current rating must match with the relay you are using. Anyway be careful to avoid the risk of electric shock while working with mains operated devices.

Here the ultrasonic ranging module is placed on top of the tank facing the water surface. The water reflects the ultrasonic pulses emitted by the module. The module picks the reflected waves and also measures the time lag. The distance between the water surface and the sensor is calculated from the collected data and the module outputs a pulse whose width is proportional to the distance. The microcontroller reads the width of this output pulse and does necessary maths on it to get the distance. Here we can see that the water level is measured from top to bottom unlike most sensors which measure the level from bottom to top. This is done to make this device suitable for a wide range of depths. Since the sensor is placed on top of the tank we need to subtract the distance from the sensor to the water surface from the total depth of the tank in order to get the level of water from bottom to top. Since different tanks have different depths the individual user has to measure the depth of the tank manually and alter the program with this data.

This problem is solved by measuring the level from top to bottom. Here the device switches ON the pump when the level falls below 5 cm from top and switches OFF the pump when the level rises to 5 cm from top. The level displayed on the LCD screen is actually the depth of the water surface from top. Tanks with depth up to 1.5 meters will go well with this project.

3. Software Description

Keil development tools[11] for the 8051 Microcontroller Architecture support every level of software developer from the professional applications engineer to the student just learning about embedded software development.

The Keil μ Vision Debugger accurately simulates on-chip peripherals (I²C, CAN, UART, SPI, Interrupts, I/O Ports, A/D

Converter, D/A Converter, and PWM Modules) of your 8051 device. Simulation helps you understand hardware configurations and avoids time wasted on setup problems. Additionally, with simulation, you can write and test applications before target hardware is available.

4. Experimentation setup

A rectangular water tank was used to test the proposed measurement system. The tank was fitted with an ultrasonic sensor near the top left of the tank. The actual level readings were obtained using a scale ruler attached vertically to the tank

5. Statistical Results

Statistical observations of the proposed method are discussed in this section. The correlation, error rate and limits of agreement were calculated using a correlation plot, sum of squared error (SSE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE)[15].

To examine the resolution of the proposed system, 39 readings of the actual water level in cm were compared with the measured water level and analysed using MATLAB.

Fig. 4 Matlab

Min error = 0.1 cm
 Max error = 0.3 cm
 RMSE = 0.13107
 MAE = 0.089744

5.1 Matlab code

Actual = [0.5, 0.7, 1, 1.1, 1.5, 1.8, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5, 4.8, 5, 5.5, 5.8, 6, 6.5, 7.1, 8.2, 8.5, 8.7, 9.1, 9.3, 9.5, 9.7, 10.1, 10.5, 10.9, 11.5, 12, 12.3, 12.5, 12.8, 13.5, 13.8, 14.2

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14.5,14.6, 14.8];
Observed = [0.4, 0.9, 1, 1.4, 1.5, 1.9, 2.4, 3,
3.4, 4.1, 4.8, 4.9, 5.0, 5.3, 5.8, 6, 6.6, 7.3,
8.2, 8.8, 8.7, 9.2, 9.3, 9.5, 9.9, 10.1, 10.6,
11.2, 11.5 12, 12.4, 12.4, 12.9, 13.5, 13.8,
14.3, 14.6, 14.6, 14.9];
plot(Actual, Observed, '.', 'MarkerSize', 15),
xlabel('Actual Data (cm)'), ylabel('Observed
data (cm)');
grid on
hold on
x= 0:15;
y=x;
plot(x,y, 'r', 'LineWidth', 2 )
Diff= Actual-Observed;
Square= Diff.*Diff;
Sum= sum (Square, 'all');
Div= Sum/39;
RMSE = sqrt(Div);
disp(['RMSE is ', num2str(RMSE)]);
Sum2= sum (Diff, 'all');
MAE= Sum2/39;
disp(['MAE is ', num2str(MAE)]);

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6. Conclusion

The ultrasonic sensor 8051 microcontroller has been used to quite accurately measure the water level and with an automatic control circuit to fill the tank and provide early warning of water surplus or deficiency. Here the device switches ON the pump when the level falls below 5 cm from top and switches OFF the pump when the level rises to 5 cm from top. Although several types of sensors (electronic or/and optical sensors) had been already proposed previously with higher resolution for the level monitoring task, the system we propose based on the ultrasonic sensor present quite a few advantages, such as simplicity, cost effectiveness, portability and energy efficiency. The maximum error was approximately 0.1 cm. However, further studies on robustness, the environmental temperature conditions, and detection range are needed to consider and achieve better outcomes.

7. References

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